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A Socio-Semantic Study Of Toponyms Of Urban Place Names Of Some Selected Names In Birnin Kebbi Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The academic pursuit of researching names of all kinds, encompassing linguistics and other related sciences, is known as onomastics. It examines how names are transferred between categories and focuses on differentiating names from words. However, in Birnin-Kebbi metropolis, many people bear different ward names without knowing their origin and meanings; aside from the fact that there is a dearth of research work on onomastic analysis of names commonly practiced in this city. This work therefore aims at conducting an onomatological analysis of some selected place names of urban of the Birnin-Kebbi metropolis in Kebbi State. To achieve this aim, this study: explored how naming practice in Birnin-Kebbi were shaped by social factors, in order to discover how names contribute to the construction and negotiation of social identity; uncovered how naming practices reinforce or challenge existing power structures, including issues of dominance, marginalisation and resistance within place names in the Birnin-Kebbi; examined how Language Context in a Multicultural Context Influences Naming Practice; and, explained Meaning behind the place names and the People of Birnin-Kebbi, and how they Contribute Communication and Identity. The data used in this study consists of 50 names of settlements in the urban settlements of the Birnin- Kebbi metropolis. The data were collected using 70 questionnaires and interviewing 12 history custodians. By employing the onomastic theoretical framework, the study discovered that the names of settlements in Birnin-Kebbi metropolis were shaped by social factors such as natural features, occupational influences, infrastructure; government policies and regulations, migrations, etc. it was also discovered that naming practices reinforce or challenge existing power structures, including issues of dominance, marginalisation and resistance within ward names in Birnin-Kebbi. Moreso, meanings of names reflected social identity. The study concluded that ward names are more than just words; they are a center of history that can link the past and present.

Keywords: Toponymy, onomastics, linguistics, Birnin-Kebbi

INTRODUCTION

This paper seeks to explore the uniqueness of Toponymical study of some selected urban place names of settlements in Birnin-Kebbi metropolis. This study is a linguistic exploration of name of urban settlements in Birnin-Kebbi Metropolis. Olaleye and Dahunsi (2019, p.85) submit that “the linguistic act of naming a new baby in Nigeria as an example involves a conscious effort of name-givers to reflect certain variables like: religion, sex, culture, etc. and circumstantial values of the baby”. Going by this submission, it is expected that naming practice both in the ancient and the new Birnin-Kebbi Metropolis would reflect the realities stated in the submission. Crystal (1997, p.112) asserts that the science that studies name is known as Onomastics. Onomastics is the branch of linguistics that is concerned with the study of names. It can be categorized into four major branches: Toponymy is concerned with place names Ethnonymy studies ethnic names; Anthroponomy deals with personal names, Charactonymy studies literary names.

Names are as old as man himself. This explains why Algeo and Algeo (2000) said that the use of name is generally central to humans and human activities. Name is therefore an indispensable part of human existence. According to the scriptures of the two major religions in Nigeria (The Glorious Qur'an and the Holy Bible), God created man and named him Adam/Adamu. His companion was subsequently created and named Eve/Hauwa. In view of the above, names have been there since the creation of the universe, after the creation of Adam/Eve, God commanded Adam to give names to other Creatures. The Holy Qur'an (2:33) says: O Adam! Inform them of their names. Then when he had informed them of their names, He (God) said: "Did I not say to you that I surely know what Ghaib (unknown) in the heavens is and the earth and (that) I know what you manifest and what you hide?" Likewise, in the book of Genesis (2:19), the Holy Bible says: "Whatsoever the man called every living creature, which was the name thereof." Oseni (1981).

Language choice is shaped by social-factors. Naming practice is greatly shaped by these social factors. Several researches have been conducted in the field of Onomastics, for examples, Dauda 2002/2003), Ahmed (2013), Rashidat (2014), Chamo (2013), and Olaleye and Dahunsi (2019). Most of these studies, however, revolve around anthroponomy i.e. the study of personal names. In the area under consideration, few toponymical studies exist. Mustapha's (2001) research work deals with Hausa geographical names with emphasis on Kano metropolis. Interestingly, Birnin-Kebbi remains a very important component of Northern Nigerian History. Birnin-Kebbi metropolis holds many relics of Pre-colonial and colonial history. However, in Birnin-Kebbi metropolis, many people bear different settlement names without knowing their origin and meanings; aside from the fact that there is a dearth of research work on onomastic analysis of names commonly practiced in this city. This study therefore intends to fill this gap by conducting an onomatological analysis of place names of Birnin-Kebbi metropolis in Kebbi State. Therefore, socio-semantically, this is the gap the study seeks, to fill in the field of Onomastics.

This inquiry will hopefully reveal relevant information on the Settlement and Land Reclamation, the Economic Activities and Political Developments. By this, the study will connect the Past Generation with the modern generation of Birnin-Kebbi Inhabitants.

Therefore, the major objectives of this study are:

- i. To explore how naming practice in the ancient and the new Birnin-Kebbi are shaped by social factors, in order to discover how names contribute to the construction and negotiation of social identity;
- ii. To uncover how naming practices reinforce or challenge existing power structures, including issues of dominance, marginalisation and resistance within ward names in the new and the ancient Birnin-Kebbi;
- iii. To examine how Language Context in a Multicultural Context Influences Naming Practice; and,
- iv. To explain Meaning behind the Ward names and the People of Birnin-Kebbi, and how they Contribute Communication and Identity.

The researcher will seek to answer the following research questions:

- i. How naming practice does shapes the Ward names of the ancient and the new Birnin-Kebbi metropolis through social factors?
- ii. How does naming practice uncover Marginalization and resistance of Ward names of the ancient and the new Birnin-Kebbi metropolis?
- iii. How language context in a Multicultural does influences naming Practice in Ward names of the ancient and the new Birnin-Kebbi metropolis?
- iv. How does meaning of the Ward names and the people of Birnin-Kebbi metropolis contribute to communication and identity?

Definition of Names

Name is an ancient word whose history could be traced to Indo European honen. This has produced Latin nomen sources of English words such as nominate, noun)... (Source of English anonymous etymologically nameless and synonym, welsh enw, and Russia imja, among others. In Pre-historic German descendant was namon, which has evolved to German and English name, Dutch naam, Swedish navn, and Danish nyan. Ayto (in Ahmad 2016, p.107).

Mphande (2006, p.106) submits that "names, as words by which reality is known and spoken of, are the most meaningful lexicon in the vocabulary of any language, and they are an important part of the language inventory as they not only name the environment, but also store all the distinctions about the fauna and flora". Everyone has a name; some people have multiple names.

Ahmed.A, et al (2016) defines name as the specific word or words used to denote a member of a particular class of beings or objects. Similarly, Hyder (1978) sees name as an image of the things it represents. Name can, therefore, reflect the culture, tradition, experience and value of tplace of origin or people of a particular culture through names of their wards and streets.

Approaches to Naming

Makando and Edwards, in Abdurashed (2012, p.140), assert that although the phenomenon of naming practices is universal, previous studies indicate that different approaches for naming are involved in different cultures, countries or social settings. Different cultures have different orders for giving names and surnames. In western culture, given names precede family names. Moyo, in Abdurashed (2012, p.140), argues that the practice of surname before first name is Chinese, Vietnamese, Hungarian and Romanian cultures. He further stresses that people consider family more important than individual identity. Among the Hausa, given names precede surname, In this regard, when one addresses another individual with his/her surname, it is considered an insult, because Hausa culture holds in high esteem surname As such, names of Mother - in - laws, father-in-laws, first child are replaced by nicknames.

Atoma (2006) identify five of these facets: the geographical, the historical, the linguistic, the symbolic, and the socio-political facets. This study is concern about the geographical facets

Geographical facet: One of the prominent functions of names, in general is to empower, the users to refer to the entities named. This is of paramount importance in the case of toponyms. As the work by Peter E. Raper (2004) shows, identifying and referring unambiguously to geographic entities is pivotal to most human activities today. This statement holds true also for ethnonyms. In order for toponyms and ethnonyms to refer unambiguously many linguistic, pragmatic, socio-cultural and intercommunicative conditions must be met. In the case of African onomastics, the satisfaction of these conditions is sometimes hindered by many obstacles, some of which are due to the colonialism.

The Concept of Toponymy

Greek philosophers were among the earliest people to carry out studies on names. Aristotle had, earlier, distinguished between appellatives (which relates to the giving of a name) and propria (which relates to the ownership of a title). Blanár (2009, p.92-94) notes that though the Stoics provided the first definition of proper names as designating an individual whose certain meaning is embodied in her or his specific

characteristics (individual lekton), it was Aurelius Augustinus who first provided the semiotic meaning of proper names in his theory of signs. Blanár (2009) further explained that this semiotic feat, which was later expanded by Dionysios Thrax (170-90 BC). A Hellenist and Aelius Donatus, the Roman grammarian (circa 350 AD) defined a proper name as a sign of individual substance. He believed that general names should be signs of general substances such as girl, boy, pig, building, river, etc.

Algeo (2000) asserts that the use of name is generally central to humans and human activities. It is against this backdrop that they consider the interconnections of onomastics with such disciplines as medicine, anthropology, business, linguistics, folklore, literature, before focusing on the role of place-names. As such, it is situated at the crossroads of various disciplines. The Romanian linguist, Al. Graur affirmed that place names and person names "constitute a piece of the tradition and the history of our country as they bear information on the culture and, in general, on the way of living of those who preceded us" (Graur, 1972, p.10). Since toponymy deals with the study of the origin, meaning and evolution of place names in a certain language, it will raise the interest of the geographer, the historian and that of the linguist and philologist. Furthermore, as human speech is directly linked to a particular culture, toponymical research can help to investigate the evolution of a language, the origin of words, their meaning and semantic evolution) and, most importantly, the cultural evolution of the nation that speaks that particular language.

Types of Toponymy

Toponymy can be divided into two; synchronic and diachronic. From a **synchronic** point of view, since Toponymy only exists in connection with human society and history, it represents a linguistic image of the history of a certain region; so that any geographical name is history expressed by means of the laws of the language. Moreover, synchronic research highlights the means of word formation in Toponyms in the current stage, which involves the analysis of the relationships between their components, of the modality and succession of combination in the process of word formation. Nonetheless, not all Toponyms represent modern formations, as many are considerably old, and, in many cases, ancient Toponyms contain elements that no longer exist in the modern language or are formed according to rules that are unknown to present-day speakers. This leads to the necessity.

For a **diachronic** approach of word formation in the case of place names, in toponymy, this diachronic aspect is included in the origin and evolution of place names. Old toponyms that have lost the morphological connection with their basic words are studied in a diachronic approach, and the structure of such place names is determined with the help of the etymological analysis. The diachronic research of a toponym also consists, on the one hand, in a time analysis, of the changes that occurred in the relation of designation, and, on the other hand, in the investigation of the succession of relationships between the toponym in question and other toponyms which designate other elements of the same geographical or socio-geographical complex.

Authorial Review

Unarguably, Birnin-Kebbi constitutes a very the pre-colonial significant part of Northern Nigerian. Surprisingly, scholars of Hausa place names in northern Nigeria have not yet enquired into Place names of Birnin-Kebbi Metropolis. Hence, this study intends to inquire into the system of Hausa place names in Birnin-Kebbi metropolis.

Achenyo (2015) studies the shades of meaning of igala names. She adopts semiology as the a theoretical framework to reveal the naming She system in Igala culture. He concluded that names are bond to semiology because linguistically, names are analyzed as sign and semiology is the science of signs. Emetu (2009), studies the Sociolinguistics analysis of names in Anambra state. The study identifies that context determines the meaning of a word (names) or utterance as they are received and perceived by the society.

Bachan, Anyanwu et al (2017) in their research selected one hundred (100) toponyms from different parts of India and Nigeria. They analysed them in order to show the development of place-names in both countries in the new millennium. The research concluded that while India is making serious efforts towards a complete linguistic independence, through the development of place-names, Nigeria is

promoting anglicised place-names, which is detrimental to the development of indigenous Nigerian languages.

Chamo (2013) analyses the values of Hausa traditional names and explains their contextual meanings and symbols as names are regarded as significant aspect in Hausa society. He looks at the Hausa names from the sociolinguistic point of view which considers names as socio-cultural tags that have socio-cultural functions and meanings. The work discusses the typology of Hausa Traditional names. These include (1) Positional names, (2) Manner names, (3) Circumstantial names. (4) Death prevention and survival names, (5) Periodic or seasonal names, (6) Theophoric names, and (7) based on physical appearance. He argues that Hausa names are not arbitrary but they are given based reasons on socio-cultural and ethno-pragmatic reasons. He concluded that there is a strong interface between a people's language and their cultural practices. Mustapha (2001) carried out a linguistic study of the names of Wards in contemporary Kano city. He categorized the ward into eight derivative classes. He concludes that six of the derivatives are of natural geographical features while the last two are either vividly of the descriptive or have an unclear etymology.

Socio-semantic refers to the study of how social context and cultural factors influence the meaning of language. Socio-semantic combines the study of social relationships and the relationship between concepts.

The word socio- is seen by many as either a prefix to a content concept, in this review, it is seen as a combining form that denotes social or the society. A combining form of meaning, "social", "sociological", "society" etc, in the context of the review, "socio-semantics", where social, societal and sociological usage of language meaning meets.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Onomastic views on names which are based on the theory that there is a strong interface between people language and their cultural practices. This study adopts Firth's (1957) contextual theory of meaning. According to him, every utterance occurs in a culturally determined context of situation, and the meaning of an utterance is the totality of its contribution to the maintenance of that pattern of life in the society in which the speaker lives and to the affirmation of the speaker's role and personality within the society. Hence, this framework is considered best suited for this study. Firth himself notes that the meaning of an expression will consist in a serial contextualization of facts, context within context, each one being a function, an organ of the bigger context and all the contexts finding a place in what might be called context of culture.

The research in this study is a descriptive survey design. It involves it involves collecting data through surveys, interviews, or observation.

The study was carried out in some selected urban settlements of Birnin-kebbi metropolis. The data for this research was collected at the concerned settlements, traditional institutes and state history bureau. The research uses qualitative approach in analyzing the data collected. The used instruments include questionnaire, dairy, and note book. A total of 70 questionnaires were dispersed to selected residents of Birnin-kebbi urban settlements. The method of data adopts firth's (1957) contextual theory of meaning. The settlements names were categorized according to : Natural feature, infrastructure influence, occupational influence, migration, leaders or personality influence and Government policies and regulations.

Factors Determining the Settlement Names

Table 1 shows the reasons and factors behind the naming of some settlements in Birnin-Kebbi metropolitan wards. The major factors according to the table below are manmade land marks and descriptive futures like Bayan filin sukuwa and Bayan Texaco (behind race course and behind Texaco). Kwanar-‘yan-jakkai which means donkeys riders junction are merely descriptive. However, some settlement arc named officially by either traditional rulers or by the government for instance, Shiyar fada and Shiyar Sarakuna in Nassarawa I are named by the 16th Emir of Gwandu Usman Haliru Audu. Gesse

phase I was officially named by Abubakar Musa Garkuwan Yauri who was the first democratically elected Governor of Kebbi State. More so, some settlement take their names on based occupational influence, name like mechanic area among others.

The respondent with least percentage do not know the factors responsible for their settlement names.

Table 1: Factors Determining the Settlement Names

Factors	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Natural Landmarks	7	9
Manmade (artificial) landmarks	13	16
Official names	12	15
Social influence	6	8
Descriptive features	14	18
Royal names	5	6
Occupational influence	8	10
I don't know	14	18
TOTAL	79	100%

Names Reflecting Descriptive Features

Table1 shows that some of the settlement names in Nassarawa I are mere description of the Environment. Use of Prefix Bayan which means behind is a Prime in the ward. Some settlements are named by Commercial Motorcycles Riders to describe their destinations. Bayan Filin Sukuwa (Behind the Race Course) a very large settlement situated just behind a race course and hence the name. See Table 2 below:

Table 2: Names Reflecting Descriptive Features and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Bayan Gidan Sarki	Behind the Emir's Palace Area
Bayan Tasha	Behind the Motor Park Area
Bayan Kara	Behind the Animal Market Area
Bayan Oando	Behind the Oando Filling Station Area
Bayan Filin Sukuwa	Behind the Race Course Area
Wajen Tsohuwar Kasuwa	Near Old Market Area
Bayan Gidan Waziri	Behind the Vizier's Palace Area
Bayan Kebbi TV	Behind Kebbi Television
Bayan Poly	Behind the Polytechnic
Bayan Labana	Behind Labana Rice Mill
Wajen Gidan Noma Mai Motoci	Near Popular Personality (Noma Maimotoci's) House

Table 2 shows that in modern Birnin-Kebbi, certain settlement names arc given with reference to some picturesque images that are often described by some certain speakers for easy identification by hearers. For example, Bayan Poly describes Streets behind the Polytechnic. Bayan Gidan Waziri means behind vizier-s house. Most of the names are description of the environment based on some structures around them.

Names Reflecting Occupational Sites

Just like the ancient town, the modern city also has some settlements names based onoccupations of the people around the settlements. Sometimes, the names may not be theoccupation of the inhabitant but the occupational centre is located within the settlement. Mechanic village for instance, is a mechanic settlement.

Table 3: Names Reflecting Occupational Sites and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Mechanic Village	A street for mechanic workshop Area
Tasha	Motor Park Area

Table 3 shows that similarly, in modern Birnin-Kebbi metropolis, certain settlements are named after some occupations. For example, Tasha is a Settlement around Motor Parks likewise; Mechanic village is a settlement for Car Repairs.

Table 4: Names Reflecting Royal Wards and Settlements and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Shiyyar Fada	Royal Area/Settlement
Fada Junju	Royal Junju (Slaves settlement after emancipation)
Gidan Sarki	Emir's Palace
Rafin Magaji	The Mayor's River
Majalisa	

Table 4 shows that the above settlement naming were done with reference to royalty. They are names of some Royalties in modern Birnin-Kebbi. For example, Gidan Sarki means Emir's palace.

Names Reflecting Immigrant Camp

Some settlements were immigrant camp and subsequently named after a particular tribe and ethnics groups earlier inhabited the settlements. Shiyar Zabarmawa, means Zabarmawa Settlement and was first inhabited by Niger Republic, Mali, Burkina Faso and some parts of Nigeria). As a result, their language is very common in the settlement.

Table 5: Names Reflecting Immigrant Camp and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Shiyar Zabarmawa	Immigrant Settlement (from niger republic)
Shiyar Junju	Immigrant Settlement (Junju clan)
Runtuwon Fulani	Immigrant camp Area (fulani clan)

Table 5 shows that in Modern Birnin-Kebbi, certain Settlements are named after the Immigrants that Occupy the Street. For example, *Runtuwon Fulani* means Fulani Camp.

Names Describing Natural Features

Gesse which means farm land in Fulfulde language are Government Established Settlements with three phases that have so many Sub-settlements and Street names. Most of the Settlements and Streets in Gesse phase one are named after some Natural Features in the Settlements, mainly Trees. Dorawa and Murna roads for instance are named after Acacia and baobab trees that are abundant in the two streets.

Table 6: Names Describing Natural Features and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Murna biyu (Sub Settlement of Bayan Kara)	Two Baobab tress
Inwar Buzu	Buzu Shade (a mad man lived under a tree's shade)
Shiyyar Gawo Road	Winter Thom road
Tsamiya Road	Tamarind Road
Murna Road	Baobab Road
Dorawa Road	Acacia Road
Giginya Road	Arrow Root Road
Lemu Road	Orange Road
Kashumiya Road	Cashew Road
Mangwaro Road	Mango Road

Table 6 shows that certain names also emanated from Natural Geographical Features like Hill, Forest, Rock, River, Trees and Vegetation etc. For example, all the roads in Gesse phase I are named after Natural Features (trees) for easy descriptions. Some of the Trees used to Name Streets were replaced with other species or removed by the Residents, but the names remain officially. Gawo road means Winter Thom, Mangwaro means Mango Street, Kuka Street means Baobab tree; Gawasa means Ginger bread Giginya means Arrow Root.

Names Given According to Personalities

Table 7: Names Given According to Personalities and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Gidan Sarkin Zabarmawa	Head of particular clan (Zabarmawa) House
Gidan Noma Maimotoci	A prominent personality (Noma Maimotoci's) House
Umaru Gwandu Road	A prominent Person (Umaru Gwandu) Road
Col. Patrick Aziza Road	Col. Patrick Aziza Road
Ahmadu Bello Road	A prominent personality (Ahmadu Bello) Road
Ubandoma Road	District head Road
Sani Abacha by-pass	Sani Abacha by-pass
Galadima Road	Prince (Galadima) Road
Sultan Road	King (Sultan) Road
Magajin Gari Road	Mayor (Magajin Gari) Road
Magajin Rafi Road	Mayor (Magajin Rafi) Road
Justice Ibrahim Umar Road	Justice (Ibrahim Umar) Road

Table 7 shows that in modern Birnin-Kebbi, Most of the roads in especially in Gesse phase II are named after a city or a prominent personality. While some roads are named after targeted personalities, positions and titles.

Names Reflecting Government Establishments

Nassarawa, as Government Established settlements, have many Government Establishments, impact, is the centre of Administration. Usually, some settlements are named after some Government Establishments around the Settlements. Kebbi TV is a named attributed to the entire settlements around and behind the Kebbi television building. See table 21 for names and their meaning;

Table 8: Names Reflecting Government Establishments and their Meaning

Names	Meaning
Kebbi TV	Kebbi Television Area
Information	Ministry of Information Area
Health	Primary Health Care Area
Eid ground	Eid Ground Area
Race Course	Race Course Area
Investment	Investment Area
Treasury	Treasury Area
Bayana Sir Yahaya	Behind (Sir Yahaya) Hospital
Bayan School of Nursing	Behind School of Nursing
Government House Area	Government House Area
GRA	Government Residential Area
Bayan Tasha	Behind Motor Park
Bayan Kara	Behind Animal Market
Bayan CBN	Behind the Central Bank of Nigeria
Permanent site	Polytechnic campus permanent site

Table 8 shows that in modern Birnin-Kebbi, certain settlements are named after government offices and establishments. For example, school of nursing, GRA, Kebbi TV and Central Bank etc.

Summary of Findings and Discussion

- The study reveals the meaning of settlement names of the urban Birnin-kebbi metropolis emerged due to socio ecological factors and it's influenced by socio cultural dimension of the inhabitant,
- This study discovered meaning of settlement names of urban Birnin-kebbi that are attained through linguistic factors. It further shows that the use of traditional Titles have help greatly in shaping the act of practice and newness of the settlements
- The study reveals that occupation and commercial activities of the people in the settlements are also responsible for names in urban settlements of Birnin-kebbi metropolis
- The study detects that there is an intrinsic relationship between the settlement names and the people of the settlements

CONCLUSION

This study is a linguistic of settlement names adopting socio-semantic theory as a framework to reveal the meaning of selected settlements names in the urban areas of Birnin-Kebbi metropolis.

RECOMMENDATION

The various areas not covered in this study are therefore recommended for other scholars in the field of linguistic to explore.

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